

Influence of Post-Processing on the Tensile Mechanical Properties of FDM Printed ASA Test Specimens Melted in a Liquid Bath

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<p>Abstract</p> <p>The development of additive manufacturing techniques using a wide range of thermoplastic materials enables the investigation of material mechanical properties as a function of 3D printing process parameters. Printed models with complex geometries require the use of support material, followed by post-processing. Therefore, this paper examines the impact of primary post-processing on the mechanical properties of ASA type 1A test specimens, specifically the removed support material. Two batches of specimens were printed using FDM deposition technology, having been prepared for 3D printing by determining the layer thickness and the infill pattern. One batch was left at room temperature, while the other batch was melted in a liquid bath. After printing, the specimens were tested for tensile strength under ISO 527-2. The results showed an imperceptible difference between the two batches with the same ultimate tensile stress values. It can be concluded that the mechanical properties of ASA specimens remain unchanged when dissolved in a liquid bath composed of sodium hydroxide and eco-friendly tablets in 40 liters of water intended for dissolving the support material.</p>	<p>Article history</p> <p>Received: 21. 05. 2025. Revised: 07. 07. 2025. Accepted: 11. 07. 2025.</p> <p>Keywords</p> <p>ASA Specimens, FDM, Tensile Testing, Liquid Bath.</p>
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1 Introduction

Design for Additive Manufacturing has become an indispensable method for creating complex geometries [1] using a layer-by-layer process, in contrast to conventional manufacturing technologies, where material is subtracted. One of the most widely used additive manufacturing processes is fused deposition modeling (FDM), which, together with fused filament fabrication (FFF), forms a broader group known as material extrusion (MEX). A thermoplastic polymer is drawn through a heated nozzle and melted, with the amount of material released controlled [2]. In recent years, several FFF printers with heated chambers have emerged on the market, resulting in high-quality models that are similar to those used in the FDM process. FDM is a commercialized term used by the Stratasys company for the production of precision models, utilizing

nozzles to build parts and support material, which enables the creation of smooth surfaces. Therefore, the process parameters must correspond to the recommendations of the material manufacturer because the entire process is carried out under special conditions [3]. The process parameters of the FDM technique can be categorized according to the criteria of slicing parameters, building orientation, and temperature conditions [4]. They need to be carefully selected with a focus on the product application, as the parameters themselves are interdependent. Polymer parts stand out among the numerous additively manufactured components due to their low cost and excellent mechanical properties. They have a wide range of industrial applications in the automotive, aerospace, and biomedical fields, from prototypes to final products. Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the mechanical properties of thermoplastic polymers. Acrylonitrile styrene acrylate (ASA) exhibits improved material properties.

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It is an engineering thermoplastic with a molecular structure similar to acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS). It possesses better properties, such as UV and chemical resistance, as well as high strength and stiffness [5]. Printing ASA material requires a closed 3D printing environment and temperature control in the FDM additive manufacturing process.

To date, researchers have studied the mechanical properties of FDM materials only by varying their process parameters (Figure 1). The tensile strength of additively manufactured test specimens increases with decreasing layer thickness and increasing spacing between fibers (raster gap), providing a larger bonding surface area [6]. It also increases with the percentage of internal filling [7]. Arora et al. [8] attempted to optimize the FDM parameters to improve tensile properties by combining different parameters and creating interactions among them. They recommended extruder temperatures (207.5°C – 210°C), layer thicknesses (0.23 mm – 0.30 mm), print speeds (40 mm/s – 44 mm/s), and infill densities (94% - 100%). Hameed et al. [9] confirmed the influence of layer thickness and infill density on the mechanical properties of ASA test specimens using the Taguchi approach for parameter optimization. FDM parts exhibit different strengths in the X, Y, and Z build directions, indicating their anisotropic behavior.

In contrast to them, Sanford et al. [10] examined the effects of several parameters such as build orientation (flat, on the side along the length of the specimens, on the side by width of the specimens), print/infill angle (0/90°, 15/75°, 30/60°, 45/45°) and solid infill pattern (100%) for all test specimens on tensile testing. The specimens with an infill angle of 45°C exhibited the maximum ultimate tensile

stress and elongation after yielding for all build orientations, where both quantities increased with the infill angle. Additionally, the orientation of the infill pattern affects the mechanical properties due to the orientation of the melted fibers. Temperature control in the heating chamber ensures the proper formation of bonding layers in the FDM process. Maintaining a constant filament flow rate through the extruder nozzle is recommended to ensure the production of high-quality parts with stable temperature control. The thermal properties of printed parts depend on process parameters such as layer thickness and infill density. Elkholy et al. [11] investigated the anisotropic thermal conductivity of parts using the FDM additive process. They concluded that layer width is more critical than layer thickness in the case of layer debonding, which occurs due to improper bonding of layers in 3D printing. Raster gap and weak bonds occur in the printed layers, which reduce the quality of the printed part.

Post-processing processes are the final step in FDM additive manufacturing. All printed parts do not require post-processing, but this does not diminish their importance. FDM processes can be divided into removing support material, sanding, and gap filling, which is referred to as primary post-processing intended for industrial applications [12]. However, the goal of this paper is to conduct experimental tests to determine the mechanical properties of ASA specimens in tensile testing that have been previously melted in a liquid bath used exclusively for melting the support material. In this way, the overall influence of the liquid bath is examined based on both process parameters — layer thickness and infill pattern — which can later be applied to models of complex geometry where support material is necessary.

Figure 1 Significant parameters of the FDM process: layer thickness, raster angle, raster gap, raster width and contour width [19]

2 Experimental methods

To obtain high-quality validation of the mechanical properties of ASA material, it was necessary to print and perform tensile testing on at least two batches of test specimens for comparison of results. The equipment was high quality, regularly maintained, and intended for professional use.

2.1 Test specimens and experimental equipment

Type 1A test specimens with a square cross-section of 10x4 mm were prepared for tensile testing according to the ISO 527-2 standard [13]. They were modeled in SolidWorks 2018 software using the appropriate shape and dimensions in Figure 2 and Table 1. The overall length l_3 was increased by 10 mm to ensure the fixation of the test specimens in the jaws during uniaxial tensile testing, while the other dimensions remained unchanged. The FDM Stratasys F270 industrial printer from the F123 series, along with the corresponding GrabCAD Print software version 1.92.17.44384, was selected.

The nozzle diameter of 0.4 mm is the same for both nozzles, allowing for the printing of complex geometries within a working volume of 305×254×305 mm³. Since the Stratasys F270 has a closed printing environment, it only accepts original materials from its own manufacturer. ASA Black filament, type F900-T16 Tip, manufactured by Stratasys (Eden, Prairie, MN, USA), was used in this paper. A Shimadzu AGS-X universal material testing machine (Kyoto, Japan), with a capacity of 100 kN, and TrapeziumX v1.5.6 software were used for uniaxial tensile testing of specimens.

Figure 2 3D model of test specimens with appropriate labels according to the ISO 527 – 2 standard

Table 1 The appropriate shape and dimensions of type 1A test specimens according to the ISO 527-2 standard

	Specimen type	1A
l_3	Overall length ^a	170
l_1	Length of narrow parallel-sided portion	80 ±2
r	Radius	24 ±1
l_2	Distance between broad parallel-sided portions ^b	109.3 ±3.2
b_2	Width at ends	20.0 ±0.2
b_1	Width at narrow portion	10.0 ±0.2
h	Preferred thickness	4.0 ±0.2
L_0	Gauge length (preferred)	75.0 ±0.5
	Gauge length (acceptable if required for quality control or when specified)	50.0 ±0.5
L	Initial distance between grips	115 ±1

^a The recommended overall length of 170 mm of the type 1A is consistent with ISO 294-1 and ISO 10724-1. For some materials, the length of the tabs may need to be extended (e.g. $l_3 = 200$ mm) to prevent breakage or slippage in the jaws of the testing machine.
^b $l_2 = l_1 + [4r(b_2 - b_1) - (b_2 - b_1)^2]^{1/2}$, resulting from l_1 , r , b_1 and b_2 , but within the indicated tolerances.

According to the manufacturer's material data sheet [14], tensile testing was performed on the same material, ASA Black filament F900-T16 Tip, for a layer thickness of 0.254 mm, used for 3D printing of test specimens with a yield stress (S_y) of 32.8 MPa, an elongation at the yield point (E_y) of 2.5%, an elongation at the break point (E_b) of 5.9% and an elastic modulus (E_m) of 2140 MPa.

2.2 Experimental testing

Two batches of type 1A test specimens were prepared using GrabCAD Print software with the same process parameters to determine the influence of the primary post-processing on the mechanical properties of the ASA test specimens (Figure 3). Each batch consisted of five specimens, as recommended by the ISO 527-1 standard [15]. According to Ref. [10], the florientation and several process parameters can be specified in the GrabCAD software, while other parameters are automatically set and remain unchanged. The selected layer thickness of the ASA building material was 0.25 mm (typically in the range of 0.13 to 0.33 mm), which corresponded to the thickness of the filament layer tested in the manufacturer's catalog. The specimens were printed with solid infill at a 45° angle and a minimum height of the Stratasys QSR support material.

Additionally, it was crucial to adhere to the operating settings of the Stratasys 3D printer. The test specimens were placed in a heated chamber with a

Figure 3 The positioning of test specimens for 3D printing in GrabCAD software

specific print speed of 50 mm/s, a nozzle temperature of 245°C, and a bed temperature of 100°C. According to the manufacturer's recommendation, if these values are not controlled, the quality of the specimens decreases. A liquid bath was used to remove the support material from the FDM-printed parts during the post-processing phase. It consisted of one bottle of sodium hydroxide (P400) and five packages of tablets, dissolved in 40 liters of water (Figure 4). Each package contained five eco-friendly tablets, totaling twenty-five, manufactured by EcoWorks. Protective equipment should be used when handling this solution, and its disposal must follow the state's regulatory statutes. After 3D printing, the support material was first manually removed from both batches. Specimens from one batch were left at a room temperature of 22°C, while specimens from the other batch were dissolved in a liquid bath at 60°C for 24h. Afterward, both batches were prepared for tensile testing.

The Shimadzu AGS-X universal machine offers several options for testing material properties, including tensile, bending, and flexural testing. It features a common joint for tensile and compression tests, allowing for easier and faster replacement of plates and jaws. This machine reduces the number of repeated tests because the crosshead's testing speed is 1600 mm/min, and its return speed is 2200 mm/min. The TrapeziumX software provides all the necessary data for testing and transfers it from the machine via a calibration cable, allowing for one-window monitoring. The uniaxial tensile testing was performed at a room temperature of 22°C for both batches. The specimens were tested at a speed of 1

Figure 4 One bottle of sodium hydroxide P400 and one package of tablets for liquid bath

mm/min until they reached a strain of 0.5%, then continued at a speed of 20 mm/min until failure, according to the ISO 527-2 standard, which corresponds to the standard for modeled test specimens.

3 Results and discussion

The mechanical characterization of the primary ASA material was conducted in the laboratory at a room temperature of 22°C using uniaxial tensile testing, as shown in Table 2. Each specimen was tested individually using the TrapeziumX software, and then the stress-strain diagrams of specimens from the same batch were overlapped to compare the results. The specimens melted in a liquid bath represent the first batch, while the specimens from the second batch were not subjected to any post-processing.

In this paper, the symbols and abbreviations conform to the ISO/IEC directives. The results of each test show the values of ultimate tensile stress. (S_{max} or UTS), and strain (ϵ), along with their average, standard deviation, and range of both batches. According to the ISO standard [16], it is assumed that yield stress (S_y), and ultimate tensile stress points coincide, which can be confirmed by Equation (1) [17]. After the ultimate tensile stress is reached, the curve decreases until the fracture, as determined by the tensile stress at the break (S_b). Therefore, the tensile stress at break and ultimate tensile stress do not match (Equation 2).

$$S_y = S_{max} \quad \text{Eq (1)}$$

$$S_b \neq S_{max} \quad \text{Eq (2)}$$

Figure 5 Stress-strain diagrams of tensile tests for ASA test specimens melted in a liquid bath (left diagram) and left at a room temperature without any post-processing (right diagram)

Considering the results in Table 2, the average ultimate tensile stress is 32.87 MPa for the first batch and 33.61 MPa for the second batch, which are approximately equal. The percentage of infill remains at the maximum value of 100% for all test specimens. Therefore, it affects the increased material consumption, resulting in increased tensile stress [18]. All specimens have an average strain of 3.3%, which is consistent across both batches. The presented results show a negligible influence of the liquid bath, as the average results of the mechanical characterization of the ASA test specimens match.

However, the difference appears in the elongation at the break point (E_b), which also corresponds to the results visible in the stress-strain diagrams. The average value for the first batch is 6.0% (for specimens: 6.2%, 5.1%, 7.8%, 5.4% and 5.7%), while the average value for the second batch is 7.3% (for specimens: 7.7%, 8.1%, 8.3%, 5.6% and 6.8%). Several reasons may cause this non-uniformity of the results. The room temperature of 22°C was semi-controlled under laboratory conditions with deviations of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, while air humidity was not monitored. Additionally, all operating settings of the Stratasys printer were set to automatic with minimal user control. It is essential to emphasize that additively manufactured imperfections occur within the interior of the test specimens, simultaneously affecting their mechanical properties.

If the results of the experimental research conducted on both batches are compared with the manufacturer's catalog for the same material, the

values of the ultimate tensile stress match, confirming the accuracy of the laboratory tensile tests used to determine the mechanical characterization of the ASA test specimens.

When considering tensile strength, ASA is a strong material that can withstand greater impacts due to its ductility compared to PLA, which has a higher tensile strength. It is highly resistant to high temperatures, maintaining its current shape. Despite its excellent mechanical properties, this material has disadvantages due to its lack of compatibility with standard 3D printers and the specific printing conditions required for its use.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, an experimental study was conducted to determine the tensile mechanical properties of ASA test specimens. Type 1A specimens were modeled according to the ISO 527-2 standard and imported into GrabCAD software for 3D printing, with parameters such as a layer thickness of 0.254 mm and a solid infill pattern. A minimal amount of support material was removed from all test specimens printed on the Stratasys F270. For the purpose of this study, one batch was dissolved in a liquid bath composed of sodium hydroxide and twenty-five eco-friendly tablets in 40 liters of water. The specimens of the second batch were not subjected to any post-processing to facilitate comparison of the results. It was proven that the composition of the liquid bath doesn't affect the improvement of the tensile mechanical properties, as the specimens from both

batches achieved almost the same ultimate tensile stress. These results can be used in future research to define the ASA material in numerical simulations. Also, the validity of the ASA material property results was confirmed regardless of the complexity of the printed models that require the dissolution of the support material. The study can be extended by determining the geometric and mass properties of the specimens before and after post-processing, as well as by experimentally testing specimens melted in a liquid bath of a different composition than that presented in this paper.

Conflicts of Interest: The author reports there are no competing interests to declare;

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